

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF THE MYCOLOGICAL SAFETY OF FORAGE CROPS

Aliyev I.

*Azerbaijan Republic Ministry of Science and Education, Phd,
Leading researcher, Baku*

Babayeva Sh.

*Azerbaijan Republic Ministry of Science and Education, Phd,
Leading researcher, docent, Baku*

Gasimova G.

*Azerbaijan Republic Ministry of Science and Education, Phd,
docent, Leading researcher, Baku*

Akhmedova I.

*Azerbaijan Republic Ministry of Science and Education, Phd,
Leading researcher, Baku*

Gasimzadeh F.

*Azerbaijan Republic Ministry of Science and Education,
junior research, Baku*

Abstract

The presented study is devoted to the assessment of the mycological safety of forage crops. It has been found that as a result of the mentioned pathologies, significant changes occur in both the morphology and the productivity processes of forage plants. It was determined that the boundaries of Fusariosis, caused by phytopathogenic fungi such as *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Verticillium dahliae*, are quite extensive and can be found in all forage crops. At the same time, the epiphytotic occurrence of the studied phytopathogenic fungi on forage plants was observed, which can be regarded as an indicator that the level of mycological safety is unsatisfactory.

Keywords: forage crops, phytopathogens, productivity process, fusariosis, epiphytosis, mycological safety.

Although the agricultural sector constitutes a major part of our country's economy, it is able to meet only about 50% of the population's demand for agricultural products. Therefore, the expansion of cultivated agricultural areas and the increase in productivity capacity are considered among the priority directions of the agrarian policy. In recent years, the disruption of global biological balance, particularly the emergence of various diseases of different origins in cultivated plants, including forage crops, has not only reduced productivity levels but also caused significant economic losses [3,6,7].

It should be noted that combating fungal diseases within the borders of a single country has not proven to be sufficiently effective. Hence, it has become necessary to implement comprehensive measures on a regional and even global scale, including biological, chemical, and agrotechnical approaches [2,4,8]. Therefore, the study of the mycological safety of cultivated agricultural crops, including forage plants, has become one of the most relevant research topics in recent years.

Materials and methods

The research area was selected as the experimental fields of the Azerbaijan Scientific Research Institute of Crop Husbandry. The samples for the study were obtained from the probable vegetative and generative organs of forage crops cultivated in this area. For sample collection, the planned route and permanent plot methods were applied.

During the research period, more than 400 samples were collected and analyzed according to the objectives of the study. The inoculation, identification, and isolation of pure fungal cultures were carried out based on the methods and approaches currently used in mycological research [1,5,9].

For the statistical processing of the obtained results, the experiments were conducted in 4–6 replications.

Results and discussion

The growth of plants, including forage crops, whether occurring naturally or cultivated within agrophytocoenoses, in other words, in wild or cultivated forms, takes place in environments that are not sterile from a microbiological or mycological standpoint. Therefore, the interaction of these plants with microorganisms, fungi, and phytopathogens is inevitable, which consequently leads to the development of various pathologies.

It was determined that more than 80% of diseases occurring in plants, including forage crops, are caused by fungi and their phytopathogenic representatives. Examples of such diseases include Alternariosis, rust, smut, powdery mildew, wilt, gray mold, verticilliosis, cercosporiosis, phomosis, leaf spot, septoriosis, fusariosis, and ascochitosis, among others (Table 1).

The pathogens responsible for the recorded diseases belong to the following genera: *Alternaria*, *Ascochyta*, *Botrytis*, *Fusarium*, *Phoma*, *Puccinia*, *Septoria*, *Urocystis*, *Uromyces*, *Verticillium*, etc.

Table 1.

Phytopathogenic fungi detected on forage and cultivated crops and their hazard levels

№	Fungal species	Disease name	Host plant	Hazard level
1	<i>Alternaria alternata</i>	Alternariosis	Pea	2
2	<i>Ascochyta pisi</i>	Ascochitosis	Pea	2
3	<i>A. pinoides</i>	Ascochitosis	Wild pea	2
4	<i>A. imperfecta</i>	Ascochitosis	Alfalfa	2
5	<i>A. avenae</i>	Ascochitosis	Oatgrass	2
6	<i>A. hordei</i>	Ascochitosis	Wheat	2
7	<i>Botrytis cinerea</i>	Gray mold	Sunflower	2
8	<i>Cercospora beticola</i>	Cercosporiosis	Sugar beet	2
9	<i>Erysiphe graminis</i>	Powdery mildew	Wheat	2
10	<i>Fusarium avenaceum</i>	Fusariosis	Barley	2
11	<i>F. culmorum</i>	Fusariosis	Barley	2
12	<i>F. gibbosum</i>	Fusariosis	Wheat	2
13	<i>F. oxysporum</i>	Fusariosis	Barley	2
14	<i>F. solani</i>	Fusariosis	Wheat	2
15	<i>F. triticum</i>	Fusariosis	Barley, Wheat	2
16	<i>Leptosphaeria nodorum</i>	Septoriosis	Wheat	2
17	<i>Septoria nodorum</i>	Septoriosis	Barley	2
18	<i>Phoma betae</i>	Phomosis	Pea	2
19	<i>Pyenophora tritici</i>	Leaf spot	Wheat	2
20	<i>Puccinia dispersa</i>	Rust	Rye	4
21	<i>P. coronata</i>	Rust	Oatgrass	2
22	<i>P. helianthi</i>	Rust	Sunflower	2
23	<i>P. hordei</i>	Rust	Barley	2
24	<i>P. cynodontis</i>	Rust	Meadow grass	2
25	<i>Verticillium dahliae</i>	Verticilliosis	Sunflower	2
26	<i>Ustilago avenae</i>	Smut	Oatgrass	2
27	<i>U. graminis</i>	Loose smut	Sugar beet	2
28	<i>U. pisi</i>	Rust	Pea	2
29	<i>U. tritici</i>	Loose smut	Wheat	2
30	<i>U. hordei</i>	Smut	Barley	1
31	<i>Tilletia caries</i>	Covered smut	Barley	3

It was found that as a result of these pathologies, serious changes occur in the morphology, physiological-biochemical characteristics, and productivity processes of forage crops.

At the same time, during the course of the study, it was found that fungi belonging to the genera *Fusarium* and *Verticillium*, particularly *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Verticillium dahliae*, have quite broad pathogenic boundaries. Thus, fusariosis and verticilliosis were detected not only in wheat and peas but also in other species of forage crops. Therefore, such fungi that lack substrate specificity are considered universal pathogens.

Given that the recorded diseases and their causative agents were observed on forage crops, the need for a more extensive study of phytopathogenic fungi becomes evident. Comparative research has shown that both the overall mycobiota of forage crops and the individual mycobiota of specific plant species are composed approximately half, and in some cases mostly, of phytopathogenic fungi.

However, an epiphytotic occurrence of any of these phytopathogenic fungi on forage crops was also observed. This can be interpreted as an indicator that the phytosanitary condition of agrophytocenoses where

forage crops are cultivated has not reached a dangerous level.

At the same time, the frequency of occurrence of phytopathogenic fungi colonizing forage crops was also studied. It was determined that the phytopathogenic fungi considered as disease agents mostly belong to the categories of occasional and rare fungi. Since such fungi are not represented by high abundance or wide distribution, their activity is not considered dangerous as disease agents.

As a result, the phytopathogenic background in forage crop cultivation areas has not reached a virulent level, which plays an extremely important role in ensuring mycological safety.

Thus, the analytical assessment of the results obtained from the mycological studies shows that under the conditions of Azerbaijan, the phytopathological indicators of forage crops, both those growing naturally and those cultivated in agrophytocenoses, are at a satisfactory and manageable level. This is considered a highly significant factor in maintaining the productivity of forage crops

References

1. Aliyev İ.A., Babayeva Sh.A., Aliyeva F.N. Advantages of biological control methods against phytopathogenic fungi in the soil environment. / Modern Scientific Technology, Stockholm, Sweden, 2025, p:415-417 (DOI:10.5281/zenodo/15572383)
2. Aliyev İ.A., Akhmedova I.A., Aliyeva F.N. Elimination characteristics of potentially pathogenic fungi in alfalfa cultivated soils // East European Scientific Journal. 12, (97), 2023, (DOI:10.31618/ESSA.27821194,2023,1.97.432)
3. Barges R.C.F. Powdery mildew (*Erysiphe cruciferarum*) on Brassicaceae in Brazil. // Australasian Plant Pathology, 2023, vol.52, p:419-425 (DOI:10.1007/913313-023-00930-y)
4. Boland G.I., Melzer M.S., Hopkin A., Higgens V., Nassutin A. Climate change and plant diseases in Imtario // Canadian Journal Plant Pathology, 2024, vol.26, №3, p:335-350 (DOI:10.1080/070606669409500766)
5. Elbert M.K. Identification and characterization of *Cercospora beticola* necrosis-inducing effector CbNip // Mol/Plant Pathology, 2021, v.22(3), p.301-316.
6. Ellis M.B. Microfungi on Lanol plants. An identification Handbook London. Helm, 1987, 819p.
7. Lin L. Biological characteristics of *Verticillium dahliae* MAT1-1 and MAT1-2 Strains // Int.Journal Mol.Sc, 2021, v.22(13). Doi:10.3390/ijms22137148.
8. Ozeretskorskaya O.L. Problems of specific phytoimmunity // Physiology of plants. 2002, vol №1, p:148-154 (DOI: ORG/10.1023/A.1016807324924)
9. Qin F. Identification of alfalfa leaf diseases using image recognition technology // Plos One/-2016, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0168274.